

A NEXUS BETWEEN COHESION AND WRITING: ANALYZING THE USE OF GRAMMATICAL COHESIVE DEVICES IN SENIOR HIGH ACADEMIC TEXTS

Raymark Anthony P. Saluria, Jasmine Q. Beamish

Saint Louis School of Don Bosco, Inc., Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

One of the issues encountered by senior high students in their academic writing has always been the attainment of cohesion in their writing. The study sought to analyze the use of grammatical cohesive devices in the academic texts of Senior High. Furthermore, it aimed to evaluate how the grammatical cohesion is attained in the development of senior high academic texts based on the utilization of conjunctions, references, ellipses, and substitution. The study was anchored on the Model of Cohesion by Hasan and Halliday (1976). Ten (10) critique papers with a total of 275 sentences served as the raw data. This study utilized the research method of textual analysis and descriptive research. The findings revealed that 1469 grammatical cohesive devices were used in their critique papers. Additionally, conjunctions and references are more dominant in senior high academic texts. It was also reported that there is a high percentage of use of additives, appositives, and causal-conditional conjunctions while non-selective demonstrative references and existential personal references dominate the senior high academic texts.

Keywords: *Grammatical Cohesion, Academic Texts, Writing, Senior High*

INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is one of the most essential writing forms necessitated for senior high students to learn and master in the senior high curriculum. It is evident in various courses such as Reading and Writing Skills (RWS), English for Academic and Professional Purposes (EAPP), and Practical Research. The teachers' selection and

utilization of diverse academic writing tasks provide a myriad of opportunities for the students to hone their skills in this form and style of writing.

Academic writing is characterized to be clear, concise, precise, focused, open-minded, and engaging. Its purpose is to aid the readers' understanding by informing them, making arguments and claims with evidence, and persuading their readers (Hyland & Jiang, 2017).

One of the issues encountered by senior high students in their academic writing has always been the attainment of cohesion in their writing. Students find it difficult to unite the number of sentences in their paragraphs and utilize suitable transition signals in their writing. Furthermore, a comprehension problem may also occur if there is limited background knowledge on the relatedness of sentences in a text. In such cases, readers rely much on a coherent text with appropriate explicit signals to compensate for lack of prior knowledge (Alarcon & Morales, 2011).

Cohesion refers to the use of grammatical and lexical elements on the surface of the text that can form relationships among parts of the text (Tanskanen, 2006). It occurs when the semantic interpretation of some linguistic element in the discourse depends on another. It is the foundation upon which the edifice of coherence is built (Halliday and Hasan, 1985). It is expressed partly through the grammar and partly through the vocabulary (Halliday and Hasan, 1976).

The use of cohesive devices helps tie elements of a text together so that the readers know what is being referred to and how the phrases and sentences relate to each other (Harmer, 2004). The lack of understanding and awareness about cohesion especially on grammatical cohesion leads the students to use inappropriate cohesive devices. This would result to problems regarding the semantic relation among ideas in the text (Afrianto, 2017). Thus, cohesion is a prerequisite feature for any academic text if it aims to achieve its objectives.

When students write compositions, they need to establish clear relations between one sentence and the next by connecting those statements together. Good compositions establish a sense of direction by making explicit connections among their different parts, so that what is said in one sentence or paragraph not only sets up what is to come but is clearly informed by what has already been said (Alarcon & Morales, 2011). Connections can be done by using transition terms, adding pointing words, using key terms and phrases, and repeating words, but with a difference (Birkenstein & Graff, 2018).

However, the study of the concept of cohesion in academic texts has been underexplored in the Philippine research landscape. The present study was conducted to analyze the use of grammatical cohesive devices in the academic texts of Senior High. Furthermore, it sought to evaluate how the grammatical cohesion is attained in the development of senior high academic texts.

Research Questions

The study aimed to analyze the use of grammatical cohesive devices in the academic texts of Senior High students.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What grammatical cohesive devices are used by Senior High students in their academic texts?
 2. What conjunctions are utilized in the development of the academic texts?
 3. What references are utilized in the development of the academic texts?
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METHODOLOGY

Respondents and Site of Study

The subjects of the study were the Grade 12 students enrolled in the writing course English for Academic and Professional Purposes (EAPP) in the Senior High School Department for the Academic Year 2022 – 2023 at Saint Louis School of Don Bosco. Ten (10) students were taken as participants of the study taking the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) academic track.

Research Design

This study utilized the research method of textual analysis. The purpose of textual analysis is to describe the content, structure, and functions of the messages contained in the text (Caulfield, 2019). This verbal analytical discussion is based on logical statements describing the connections between the academic writers and the texts, in this case are represented by the different sentences systematically obtained from the academic texts. Moreover, it is focused on descriptive analysis of the grammatical cohesion of the writers as mirrored in their academic texts.

This study also utilized the descriptive research design. This is used to describe the variables and use as basis to develop generalizations and formulate principles or theories based on its findings (Calmorin and Calmorin, 2007). Since this study concerned with the determination of the frequency of grammatical cohesive devices such as conjunction, references, ellipsis, and substitution, descriptive research was the most appropriate design.

Sampling Technique and Data-Gathering Procedures

This study used documentation method. Ten (10) academic papers written by senior high students were obtained as raw data. The critique papers were one of the writing activities in the English for Academic and Professional Purposes (EAPP) course. The students were tasked to write a critique on the televised address of Vladimir Putin regarding his plans of conducting a 'special military operation' for Ukraine.

The ten (10) critique papers were randomly selected. A total of 275 sentences were utilized as bases of the study. In content thematic analysis, when the researcher begins to hear the same comments again and again, data saturation is being reached. Once saturation is reached, the results must be capable of some degree of generalization (Boddy, 2016). It is believed that data saturation was already achieved with the sample size.

First, each of the sentences was analyzed. The grammatical cohesive devices were identified and classified as conjunction, references, ellipsis and substitution. Next, the conjunctions were categorized as appositive, clarification, additive, variation, spatio-temporal, manner, causal-conditional, or adversative, while the references were codified as personal, demonstrative, or comparative. Finally, the utilization of grammatical cohesive devices in students' writing was analyzed.

Statistical Analysis

Percentage is used to show how the part is related to a whole. It was used in presenting the frequency percentage of the different grammatical cohesive devices.

RESULTS

Table 1
Frequency Percentage of Grammatical Cohesive Devices

Types of Grammatical Cohesive Device	Frequency	Percent
Conjunction	637	43.36
References	822	55.96
Substitution	7	0.48
Ellipsis	3	0.20
Total	1469	100.00

Table 1 presents the frequency percentage of the grammatical cohesive devices utilized in the academic texts. The findings revealed that out of 1469 cohesive devices, 822 (55.96%) are references, 637 (43.36%) are conjunctions, 7 (0.48%) are substitution, and lastly, 3 (0.20%) are ellipsis. In general, the use of references and conjunctions is dominant in the senior academic texts.

Table 2

Frequency Percentage of Conjunctions

Types of Conjunction	Frequency	Percent
Appositive	173	27.16
Clarification	38	5.97
Additive	236	37.05
Variation	25	3.92
Spatio-Temporal	17	2.67
Manner	21	3.30
Causal-Conditional	82	12.87
Adversative	45	7.06
Total	637	100.00

Table 2 shows frequency percentage of conjunctions used in the senior high academic texts. Out of 637 conjunctions, the most commonly used ones are additives with a frequency of 236 (37.05%) followed by appositives with 173 (27.16%) and causal-conditional conjunctions with 82 (12.87%). Other types of conjunctions used were adversative with 45 (7.06%), clarification with 38 (5.97%), variation with 25 (3.92%), manner with 21 (3.30%), and spatio-temporal with 17 (2.67%).

Table 3*Frequency Percentage of References*

Types of References	Subtypes	Frequency	Percent
Personal	<i>Existential</i>	232	28.22
References	<i>Possessive</i>	138	16.78
Demonstrative	<i>Selective</i>	80	9.73
References	<i>Non-Selective</i>	354	43.06
Comparative	<i>General</i>	10	1.21
References	<i>Specific</i>	8	0.10
Total		822	100.00

Table 3 showcases the number of the different types and subtypes of references used in the academic texts. Out of 822 references, the most utilized ones are non-selective demonstrative references with a frequency of 354 (43.06%) followed by existential personal references with a frequency of 232 (28.22%) and possessive personal references with a frequency of 138 (16.78%)

DISCUSSION

Utilization of Grammatical Cohesive Devices

The use of references and conjunctions is more dominant in the academic texts over ellipsis and substitution. The findings concurred with the study of Trisnaningrum et al. (2019) where the highest uses of grammatical cohesion devices were reference and conjunction. The data also pointed out that the respondents were more familiar with reference and conjunction use rather than substitution and ellipsis.

The same results are mirrored in the study by Akindele (2011). Based on her study of cohesive devices used in academic papers, it was determined that a meaningful text can only be realized if the different parts of the text are connected together as a unified whole or if it has cohesion with the use of cohesive devices. Two of the cohesive devices that are used frequently in the academic papers of senior high students are references and conjunctions.

References are used to refer to something within or outside a text. It can introduce a piece of new information and keep track of the given information in the text. Reference devices or referring expressions help in uniting the text. Also, it allows writers to avoid unnecessary repetition (Akindele, 2011).

On the other hand, Darweesh and Kadhim (2016) also cited the studies of Ferris (1994) and Field and Oi (1992), which show a positive link between the frequency of cohesive devices and the quality of writing. The studies of Jin (2001) and Liu and Braine (2005) show a significant relationship between the number of conjunctions and the quality of a text. According to Riadi et al. (2023), there is a notable relationship between the use of conjunctions and the writing quality. This is because conjunctions directly impact the clear understanding of the topic and the organization of ideas through logical connection.

Poudel and Dhankuta (2018) posit that cohesive devices contribute for maintaining unity in the paragraphs in academic writing. Texts with cohesive ties and coherence are more comfortable for the readers to comprehend and interpret the message of the writer.

Use of Conjunctions in the Development of Academic Texts

The high percentage of use of additives, appositives, and causal-conditional as cohesive devices can be attributed to the type of essay the students wrote. In argumentative texts, the purpose of the writer is to establish a claim and convince readers that the claim is valid through a set of supporting points. The writers also clearly take a stand and write as if they were trying to persuade readers to adopt new beliefs or behavior. The nature of additives, conditionals, and concessives makes it possible to

strengthen claims by establishing strong connection with their supporting premises (Alarcon & Morales, 2011).

As cohesive devices, additives operate in a succession of two sentences or independent units and establish additive relations while appositives serve to introduce an additional remark to give some examples of what has been said. On the other hand, causal-conditionals function to introduce a presupposing clause that expresses a cause (Tsareva, 2010). These conjunctions are imperative in establishing claims and connections within the text.

Tsareva (2010) notes that the conjunctions are used extensively to establish cohesive relations that hold between sentences. They establish various patterns for the organization of information in the essays. Thus, grammatical cohesion is not discerned only between two adjacent sentences. Cohesive links are often established by grammatical elements that occur in a sequence of sentences that are not adjacent.

In Halliday's (2004) concept of grammatical cohesion, conjunctions are cohesive elements not in themselves but by their specific meanings. They express certain meanings which presuppose the presence of other components in the discourse.

Utilization of References in the Development of Academic Texts

The most dominant references in senior high academic texts are non-selective demonstrative references and existential personal references.

As cited from the study of Maes et al. (2022), Levinson et al. (2018) posit that demonstratives including *this* and *that* are the most frequently used words in the languages of the world. These words help the writer make references within a text to the other portions of the text. Demonstratives give a clear connection between words, sentences, and paragraphs allowing cohesion to be achieved in a specific text.

Gray (2010) cited that style manuals discourage writers from using demonstratives such as *this*, *that*, *these*, and *those* to function as pronouns to attain cohesion. On the contrary, it was also stated that many linguistic investigations determined that demonstratives function as both determiners and pronouns in academic texts.

As asserted by Rustipa (2015), it is explained in the study of Zaki (2011) that demonstratives are essential since they direct the reader to keep the recognition of the intended referent (the word being referred to).

In the pragmatic sense, demonstratives are crucial in the logical organization of information in the text. With or without new information, they can revive the previously stated referents. In the same manner, demonstratives can also establish new referents in the text. In addition, they give a reference to what the writer is implicitly or explicitly writing (Zaki, 2011). There is a need for the careful use of demonstratives as the understanding of their meaning depends largely on context and inference (Rustipa, 2015).

Based on the case study of Rustipa (2015) on the use of demonstrative pronoun and demonstrative determiner *this* in upper-level student writing where she interviewed five graduate students on the use of demonstrative *this*, it was determined that they used demonstratives in their essays to make their text coherent and achieve a unified whole.

Another reason is to establish context for the text that would follow and to maintain the theme-rheme structure. Lastly, demonstratives were used to create a variation in the style of writing to develop a more interesting text.

Moreover, the dominance of existential personal references in the academic texts was crucial in establishing connections within the texts. In the case study of Msuya (2016) that explores the author visibility in academic writing, the impersonal pronouns are the most commonly used type of pronoun even for the sections that authors can be expressive such as acknowledgment. The study concluded that academic writers strictly abide by the norms and conventions of academic writing of being overly formal and restricting the use of first-person pronouns.

Based on the findings of the study of Nurhidayah (2019), personal reference was the reference cohesive device most commonly used by the students in their essays. Additionally, they have categorized these personal references into three types, namely personal pronouns, possessive pronouns, and possessive determiners. Out of the three types, personal pronouns were used the most, followed by the possessive pronouns.

The high frequency of use of reference as cohesive device can be attributed to the fact that types of reference are used grammatically as part of a sentence as either subject, modifier or object. The relationship between things or facts may also be established with the use of reference items. The low frequency of comparison both general and specific as cohesive device could suggest that there is no need to compare ideas or things in an argumentative text or the students might have used other devices to compare aside from *more, less, other* etc. (Alarcon & Morales, 2011).

Conclusions

Based on the analyses and the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- a.) As grammatical cohesive devices, conjunctions and references are more dominant in senior high academic texts compared to ellipsis and substitution as they establish connectedness among the different parts of the text and attain meaningful organization of ideas through logical connection.
- b.) There is a high percentage of use of additives, appositives, and causal-conditional conjunctions in senior high academic texts. These cohesive devices were largely instrumental for the writers to take a stand and persuade their readers by strengthening their claims and establishing strong connection with their supporting premises.
- c.) The most dominant references in senior high academic texts are demonstrative non-selective and personal existential, which are utilized to make references within an academic paper to the other portions of the text and provide a vivid connection among words, sentences, and paragraphs allowing cohesion to be achieved in a specific text.

Recommendations

Since the use of cohesive devices is indicative of the quality of academic writing of senior high students, there is a necessity to reinforce the teaching of grammatical cohesion in English classes in the junior high level. Further, there is a need to explore the lexical cohesion of the texts to further comprehend the challenges of the student writers in utilizing cohesion and coherence in academic texts. The results would supplement the findings of the present study.

Future researchers can extend the present study by using other forms of academic papers as bases of analyses such as research papers or concept papers. Future researchers may also concentrate on other types of texts such as creative, journalistic, or literary texts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors carefully evaluated all the necessary ethical considerations throughout the duration of the conduct of the study. Information consents were obtained from the participants allowing the researchers to utilize their papers as bases for textual analyses. The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were also ensured. No conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. Furthermore, plagiarism was strictly and firmly avoided and respect for intellectual property was highly achieved. There was no prejudice in the analysis of the results and that, the findings were used purely for research.

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REFERENCES

- Afrianto, A. (2017). *Grammatical cohesion in students' writing: a case at Universitas Teknokrat Indonesia*. LEKSEMA: Jurnal Bahasa Dan Sastra, 2(2), 97-112.
- Akindele, J. (2011). *Cohesive Devices in Selected ESL Academic Papers*. In *Cohesive Devices* (p. 99). Retrieved May 21, 2024, from http://nobleworld.biz/images/Akindele_AN3.pdf
- Alarcon, J. B., & Morales, K. N. S. (2011). *Grammatical cohesion in students' argumentative essay*. Journal of English and Literature, 2(5), 114-127.
- Birkenstein, C., & Graff, G. (2018). *They say/I say: The moves that matter in academic writing*. WW Norton & Company.
- Boddy CR. *Sample size for qualitative research*. Qual. Mark. J. 2016;19(4):426–432. doi: 10.1108/QMR-06-2016-0053.
- Calmorin, L. & Calmorin, M.(2007).*Research methods and thesis writing*. Sampaloc, Manila: Rex Book Store, Inc.
- Caulfield, J. (2019). *Textual analysis | Guide, 3 Approaches & Examples* Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/textual->

- Rustipa, K. (2015). The Use of Demonstrative Pronoun and Demonstrative Determiner" This" in Upper-Level Student Writing: A Case Study. *English Language Teaching*, 8(5), 158-167.
- Tanskanen, S. K. (2006). *Collaborating towards coherence*, 1-207.
- Trisnaningrum, Y., Alek, A., & Hidayat, D. N. (2019). *Discourse analysis of grammatical cohesion devices in college students' academic writing essay*. *IJEE (Indonesian Journal of English Education)*, 6(1), 79-90.
- Tsareva, A. (2010). *Grammatical cohesion in argumentative essays by Norwegian and Russian learners*. Master's thesis.
- Zaki, M. (2011). *The semantics and pragmatics of demonstratives in English and Arabic*. Universitäts-und Landesbibliothek Sachsen-Anhalt.